

Strategic Management in Building Designs for Sick Building Syndrome Control: The Effect of Ideal Building Orientation

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Abstract

Building occupants sometimes experience unhealthy symptoms or fall sick with such conditions as irritations of the throat, eyes, nose, lethargy and sometimes dizziness due to Sick Building Syndromes (SBS). This study aimed to measure that ideal building orientation reduces the effect of SBS on Occupants and proper management of the design process can reduce the formation of SBS using Northern Cyprus Buildings as case study. The estimated cases of SBS in North Cyprus are at least 909 residential units. Out of the 2252 Responses in North Cyprus, 909 Respondents (40.3%) stated they have seen an SBS building, while 293(13%) have lived in one at some point. 1343(59.6%) reported to have never seen an SBS building. The Occupants of two residential flat buildings formed the study population and twenty-six (26) sample sizes were chosen and the twenty-six (26) respondents were selected (thirteen from each building) to test how ideal building orientation can minimize the effect of SBS on Occupants and even discourage SBS formation. Data received from 80% of the respondents making twenty-one (21) respondents (9 from building A and 11 from building B) shows that building orientation affects to a large extent indoor air quality and lighting. Ideal management of building orientation design construction minimizes the effect of SBS on Occupants and guarantees the improved health of the Occupants. This paper intends to discuss the overall building management steps towards prevention of SBS formation in buildings.

Keywords: *buildings, construction, architecture, sick building syndrome*

Introduction

Occupants of Buildings often times complain about ill health's that seems to be related to the state of the building and they surprisingly become well once they leave the building they occupy. This is a situation termed as 'Sick Building Syndrome' (SBS). The term Sick Building Syndrome (SBS) is used to describe situations whereby the Occupants of a building experiences unhealthy general symptoms or fall sick with such conditions as irritations of the throat, eyes, nose and also lethargy and sometimes dizziness (1). Wargocki in his book went further to state that these health issues and problems appears to be experienced when the Occupants occupy or spend time in a building and the malaise normally stops after they have left the building or no more Occupants of the said building. (2)

Many of these complaints as stated above may be localized on a particular building type, a particular section or floor of the building or the building as a whole (3). Symptoms like dry cough, dry and itchy skin, Nose bleeding, heart palpitation, exhaustion after a little activity, joint pains, swellings of the legs, ankles and trunk, pregnancy challenges like miscarriages and even drowsiness are known to be causes of "sick building syndrome"(4).

A building can be said to be “Sick” if at least 20% of its Occupants suffer from mentioned health issues and also, if an end user have symptoms of SBS but on leaving the particular building get relieved of those symptoms. The effect of the malaise is that it reduces the efficiency of the Occupants and brings about discomfort on what might be seen as a daily normal life routine in the case where such building is a workplace, employee might find they are not able to produce maximally as they are affected by the “Sick Building Syndrome” (5). Notwithstanding complaints of symptoms might be from other causes. These may include Psychological factors, Dissatisfaction, family lifestyle, Job related stress or stress from family issues, alleges etc. (4).

Mølhave also argues that the term “Sick Building” is often used not because building fall sick but that it is because it makes Occupants sick. He went further to say that in such cases where there is an issue of SBS, Diagnosis of the buildings problem should be done, and getting its remedy and its application should be a normal procedure(1).

There have been numerous investigations on this subject matter but this research intends to show how ideal orientation of building minimizes the effect of SBS on the Occupants. In other studies different experts suggests that the temperature humidity or the air-conditioning systems are to be blamed for the SBS formations, while others suggest that chemicals contained on building materials are the cause, and while some suggests fungi as a primary cause (6,7).

North Cyprus and SBS Issues

Cyprus has gone through a rapid rebirth, growth and a remarkable but unplanned development. This development has resulted in a multitude of Building problems, aggravated also by the tourism industry. Due to this, many buildings were designed as to meet needs for housing and less emphasis placed on the overall health of the Occupants (8). In North Cyprus, there have been cases of “Sick Building Syndrome” and many of them have remained largely unreported. In recent on field research study, the number of buildings with SBS related issues was found to be high. These residential buildings with extreme cases of SBS are estimated to be as many as at least 909 housing units that include apartment buildings and bungalows. Investigation report of Kato Lakatamia in Cyprus by the Ministry of Health (2005) stated that a worldwide reported case of cancer clusters has been on the increase over the last two decades and the threat is growing in number because of environmental factors. Furthermore, it is medically proven that Asbestos particles in the air could cause cancer and some of these particles are from building (9, 10).

Table 1 : Number of Reported cases of SBS in North Cyprus

SBS BUILDINGS IN CYPRUS				
CITY	NO (RESPONDENT)	SEEN	LIVED	NEVER SEEN
LEFKOSA	772	352	67	420
LEFKE	228	167	47	61
GIRNE	301	112	28	189
MAGOSA	951	278	151	673
TOTAL RESPONDENT	2252	909	293	1343

The estimated cases of SBS in North Cyprus are at least 909 residential units. Out of the 2252 Responses from the investigation in four cities in North Cyprus, 909 Respondents (40.3%) stated they have seen an SBS building, while 293(13%)lives or have lived in one at some point. 1343(59.6%) reported to have never seen an SBS building. Nine hundred and nine (909) respondents when shown pictures of a typical SBS building ascertained they have personally experienced or seen buildings showing signs of SBS, though in variance stages of occurrence. Undoubtedly from this study, there is a well-established connection between the SBS and the health of the Occupants. The capital city of Lefkosia has at least 352 housing units in advanced stage of SBS, 112 units for Girne and 167 and 278 for Lefke and Magosa respectively. The critical level of SBS prone buildings in North Cyprus is alarming and until something is done, the residents should continue to expect rise in SBS related ailments on Occupants. The major challenge has been on how to measure and know before time SBS prone building and what can be done to remedy such effects. In many instances questions arises on how to prevent completely the development of SBS in Residential buildings or what characteristics of the building reduces the effect of the SBS on Occupants.

Due to high cost of “curing” SBS in buildings, many buildings have remained in that state due to cost. The main logic behind these SBS buildings in North Cyprus is that some of these buildings are very old and there is no maintenance culture. Most of the problems encountered in North Cyprus are mainly issues of lack of safety control and also worthy of mention is the political state of the nation that allows for certain practises in the construction industry without proper governmental control. Also issues like improper ventilation, uneven or inadequate heat distribution; lack of damp proofing of roof decks, walls and foundation are also major contributors to SBS issues in North Cyprus. SBS issues like mould formations on the walls and roofs are as a result of build-up of moisture on the wall surface and many times due to poor ventilation of the internal spaces. Worthy of note is that the most affected of the interior spaces are the bathroom and the bedrooms, in the course of this research there were few noticeable mould formations in the living rooms. This shows that SBS issues is majorly not a building material problem as the case maybe as all the parts of the building were constructed using same material but other factors contribute as well.

During initial field research, 179 out of 293 SBS buildings in advanced stages of SBS discovered were not properly oriented. Most of these buildings have living areas situated at the northern façade of the building instead of the south facade of the building for greater solar access into the living areas and this fault encourages mould formation due to dampness and other SBS issues as stuffy air, drowsiness etc. This causes limited solar access into all the living areas, thereby limiting the natural effects of solar heating and influx of daylight. Emphasis were laid more on artificial systems of heating to achieve the advantages of proper orientation and the low income earners in other to minimize expenses on heating or cooling result not in using the mechanical heating system thereby exposing themselves either to heat or cold related health issues. Notwithstanding, I noticed with proper building orientation the effect of SBS on the occupants were reduced and where the building orientation is not within ideal specification there is slightly or more adverse effect of SBS on occupants.

Two building with physical evidences of SBS; similar design and construction history but with differences in their orientation will be tested to measure how their Occupants react to the SBS conditions and to show that building orientation alters the rate at which Occupants respond to SBS in buildings. This would be done by measuring the effect of SBS malaise on the Occupants of these buildings and the results are compared to see which building has more adverse effect of SBS on the occupants.

Methodology

The Building Analysis

Picture

1: Shows the Case Study Buildings (Source: Author)

To understand these results better it will be ideal to study the two buildings, their similarities and difference in orientation. The buildings both share similar designs; constructed at the same period in 1998 by the same workforce, also have same finishes. The buildings are located in Girne North Cyprus and also the Occupants of both buildings works for the same company and have lived in the building for at least two and half years. The easily recognizable difference is that their orientation is different and this study intends to show that differences in their orientation altered how the Occupants responds to the SBS present in both building. Both buildings already shows physical signs of different stages of SBS formation

In this case study, investigations were carried out on two similar buildings named A and B. The Occupants were interviewed and also given questionnaires to examine how they respond to the buildings. The Occupants of these residential flat buildings formed the study population and twenty-six (26) sample sizes were chosen by the Taro Yamane's Model. The twenty-six (26) respondents were selected using the simple random sampling system or technique (thirteen from each building).The Questionnaires contains three section and twenty-six respondents living in the two building received the questionnaire. The three sections are:

- The health issues noticed while occupying the building
- Assessment of the Occupants activities in the building
- Occupants level of control over their living condition.

Data was received from 80% of the respondents making twenty-one (21) respondents. For Building B, Eleven (11) respondents out of thirteen respondents returned their questionnaire. While for Building A, Nine (9) Respondents returned their questionnaires out of thirteen respondents. All the data obtained through the field study was presented by the way of tables. This is to obtain a properly understood and evaluated research results. The questions and various responses were analyzed and presented.

This work introduces important steps in testing how SBS effect on the Occupants can be minimized in residential building through ideal building orientation. Responses from Occupants clearly give a better understanding on how the several Occupants react differently to the same "Sick Building Syndrome" (SBS) due to differences in the building orientation. The Occupants were interviewed and also given questionnaires to examine how they respond to the SBS buildings. This test will show Occupants respond differently during the time period they occupied the buildings under investigation.

Results and Responses

Table II: Do you Experience any of the listed condition as an end user?

Item	Conditions	Frequency of Response			
		Often	Always	Sometimes	Never
1	Lack of air	5	-	3	1
2	Very cold	3	-	6	-
3	Stuffy	7	2	-	-
4	Very dim	2	2	3	2
5	Foul smell	1	4	4	-
BUILDING B					
1	Lack of air	1	-	4	6
2	Very cold	3	-	8	-
3	Stuffy	1	-	4	6
4	Very dim	-	-	6	5
5	Foul smell	2	6	3	-

Table II: Shows Respondents agree there are Issues of SBS in their building

From table II, In Building A the respondents numbering nine agreed to a large extent the unfavorable SBS causative conditions present in their building. While in Building B also the respondents demonstrated the same affirmation in SBS causative conditions present in their buildings. The respondents complained of cold condition especially during winter and also unpleasant odors from fungi walls, stuffiness were reported as well.

According to table III, Respondents were asked if they experience some of the ailments as stated in the table.

Table III: Shows Occupants responses to SBS related ailments.

Item	Ailment	Number of Response				
		Always	Sometimes	Often	Never	Very Frequent
1	Dry Throat/sour	2	3	3	1	-
2	Skin Issues	1	4	-	2	2
3	Aches on the head	-	5	3	-	1
4	Drowsiness / fainting	1	1	2	5	-
5	Running nose	3	3	1	-	3
BUILDING B						
1	Dry Throat/sour	-	2	1	7	1
2	Skin Issues	-	1	-	10	-
3	Aches on the head	-	2	-	9	1
4	Drowsiness / fainting	-	1	-	10	-
5	Running nose	-	3	-	8	-

From the table III, In Building A over a half of the respondents complained of sore or dry throat and other SBS ailments, while in Building B the number of respondents is far below average as ninety percent clearly has never suffered an SBS ailment as stated in the table.

Table IV: Depicts that the Occupants within the study reach had different control degrees over the conditions in their buildings.

Item	Room Situation	Number of Responses				
		None	Small	A little	Mostly	Complete
1	Temperature	-	1	6	2	-
2	Air Movement	-	1	5	3	-
3	Humidity	3	2	3	2	-
4	Lighting	-	-	3	6	-
5	Noise Pollution	6	2	1	-	-
BUILDING B						
1	Temperature	-	1	1	7	-
2	Air Movement	-	2	2	6	1
3	Humidity	1	1	1	7	1
4	Lighting	-	1	1	8	1
5	Noise Pollution	4	3	3	1	-

From table IV, In Buildings B, respondents have a higher control than Building A over temperature and there is minimal control over lighting, humidity, ventilation and noise.

Smoking indoors can also help increase the level of SBS related issues found in a building. In this building A, five (5) respondents never smokes indoors against three (3) respondents from Building B. While all respondents are habitual smokers, only two persons in Building A claim they don't smoke.

Discussion

From the data readings, it shows that the orientation of the buildings has a part to play in how Occupants respond to SBS in buildings. From the results, building A delivered a higher level of SBS symptoms on the Occupants than Building B. This agrees that the poor internal or indoor air and lighting quality encourages the effect of sick building syndromes on Occupants. Building B falls within the acceptable Ideal Orientation. The Suitable orientation for living areas can be set between 15°E-225°W of true or 'solar' south. (20°E- 230°W of true south is considered acceptable) ranges. Ideal orientation of building allows for natural lighting and Ventilation, this reduces cost of mechanical system which often times discourages Occupants from it.

Furthermore, Occupants of building B seem to have less SBS symptoms in comparison to Occupants of building A even when indoors activity which could promote SBS formation like smoking is higher in building B.

From a deeper observation, data analyzed depicts that main causes of sick buildings syndrome ailment on Occupants are factors like:

- Stuffy air
- Inadequate air supply
- Dim light
- Cold spaces
- Unpleasant odours in the living buildings

And all these mentioned above are directly connected to Ventilation and lightening and these are factors can be controlled by proper lightening and Ventilation through ideal orientation for adequate ventilation and lightening and less dependency on mechanical systems. Also considering that the two buildings share everything in common in design, time of build, same buildings materials and workforce; also the Occupants work in the same company, it clear to note that the differences in response to this SBS test can be traced to differences in building Orientation atleast within the scope of this work. Building A had more acute effect of SBS on Occupants as compared to Building B as results from the tables' shows.

Ideal Orientation reduces the effect of SBS on Occupants to a great extent. Symptoms like: Headache, Running Nose, Skin Dryness, Sore Throat, and Skin Dryness can be reduced if a building is ideally orientated. Ideal orientation allows for adequate inflow of air circulation and lightening of interior spaces. Stale air and moisture buildups are prevented when a building is ideally oriented without depending on mechanical systems to achieve this.

In North Cyprus, The Suitable orientation for living areas can be set between 15°E-225°W of true or 'solar' south. (20°E- 230°W of true south is considered acceptable) ranges. A south facing slope maximises the potential for increased access to southern sun and is adequate for greater housing densities. A slope facing the south maximizes the potential for overshadowing. Passively designed homes take adequate advantage of natural energy flows to maintain thermal comfort and multi-unit housing can also do this with good design and this helps to prevent SBS formation. This is to the fact that within this orientation axis, a building would maximally benefit from optimal ventilation and solar access into its interior spaces. Beyond this ideal orientation ventilation and solar conditions would be unfavourable.

These orientations of the building allows for the overhangs to admit or allow winter sun to access the building and also to keep out the summer sun. This will make passive heating or cooling of a building to be achieved without any efforts from the Occupants and with no added cost of the use of mechanical systems.

Example

The latitude of North Cyprus is 35°N; calculate the solar altitude of the sun as viewed from Nicosia equinoxes and solstices.

Sun angle on equinoxes = (90°) minus (latitude angle)

$$= 90^\circ - 35^\circ = 55^\circ$$

Sun angle on summer solstice = (sun angle on equinoxes) plus (23.5°)

OBI

$$= 55^{\circ} + 23.5 = 78.5^{\circ}$$

Sun angle on winter solstice = (sun angle on equinoxes minus) (23.5)

$$= 55^{\circ} - 23.5^{\circ} = 31.50^{\circ}$$

Latitudes in North Cyprus vary from about 31° north to 35° north.

The ideal building orientation is the one which has the living areas and balconies facing the south and also has good access to the winter sun. When the living areas are located on the southern facade there are optimal solar access or easier accessibility of natural solar energy into the building spaces. This will significantly reduce SBS effect or issues on the Occupants.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The characteristics of a site can determine how durable it is for passive solar design. With right characteristics, the site could help minimize the cost of a good passive solar design and this encourages SBS free and stable buildings. It is advisable always to select a site that can potentially accommodate living areas facing the southern side and outdoor or external spaces during the daytime.

A building on the North-South orientation is adequate because they enjoy great access to the sun (southern sun) with minimal overshadowing by the houses and buildings near it. During summer, buildings near a particular house design would be protected by those buildings from the low west and east sun.

In hot, dry or humid climates no heating is required; Orientation should be in such a way to exclude sun rays all year round and also to maximize the building to the cooling breezes. But this is not the case with North Cyprus climatic region as it has sometimes experience extreme weather condition but usually cold weather and very warm weather. In communities or nations where ideal orientation is not achievable, in a case where the community is of high density urban area a SBS free and efficient home could be achieved by placing the orientation design of the building on the site effectively.

Ideal orientation is a design of a building on site to achieve the principle of free solar heating in the internal spaces and also to maximize the free flow of natural air into the building. This is using the knowledge of orientation to design a building to let in winter sun into its spaces and keep out unwanted summer sun out. This can be achieved on the south elevation by applying the principle of the use of shading devices to cut off the high glow summer sun from the building and admit low angled winter sun into the building. The amount of solar energy desired in a building is directly related to the region's climatic condition. When these principles are applied we will begin to see more and more SBS free buildings and also drastically reduced effect of SBS on Occupants.

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